

The Formation and Stability of Polybromide Derivatives of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part III. The Bromination of Some μ -Substituted Benzthiazoles

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One of the objects of this series of papers (Farooq and Hunter, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 545) is to examine the effect of substituents on the formation and stability of the polybromide derivatives of heterocyclic compounds, and in this connexion it appeared desirable to re-examine more closely some of the bromo-addition compounds of 1-substituted benzthiazoles which were obtained in earlier investigations. The opportunity was also taken to extend our observations to the bromination of certain members of the group which have not received previous attention.

It was observed some years ago by one of us that treatment of a solution of 1-chlorobenzthiazole in chloroform with excess of bromine gives rise to a dibromo-addition product of the thiazole base (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1488). No particular precautions were paid, however, with regard to the exclusion of moisture from the reagents employed in the original experiment and we now find that the use of sodium-dried bromine and chloroform, which has been dried over phosphorus pentoxide in this and in other brominations described in this paper, has little or no effect on the formation of the bromo-addition compound. The dibromide of 1-chlorobenzthiazole in common with most benzthiazoles containing a free *o*- and *p*-position to the nuclear nitrogen atom, gives low values for labile bromine on iodometric titration under the usual conditions, although it regenerates the original chloro-thiazole on treatment with sulphurous acid (*cf.* Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 138 ; Farooq and Hunter, *loc. cit.*).

Attention was next directed to the tetrabromide of 1-phenylbenzthiazole to which the formula (I) was assigned by Bogert and Abrahamson some eleven years ago (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 826). The fact that this compound does not yield a sulphoxide (II) on treatment with mercuric oxide (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 126) and the

existence of the tetrabromides of pyridine (Trowbridge, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, **19**, 558) and quinoline (Grimaux, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1882, **38**, 124), however, clearly invalidate the thiazonium bromide structure and suggest that the tetrabromide probably has the formula (IV). If this is the case, it is clear that a dibromide (III), analogous to benzthiazole dibromide itself, should be the precursor of the tetrabromide obtained by bromination of 1-phenylbenzthiazole.

Actually a substance having the composition of a dibromide of the phenylthiazole is readily obtained in the presence of a lower concentration of the halogen. Both this substance and the tetrabromide give low values for labile bromine on iodometric titration, due to nuclear substitution under the conditions of the determination.

It has been shown in an earlier investigation that the bromination of 1-thiolbenzthiazole gives rise to a tetrabromo-addition compound which yields benzthiazolyl-1:1-disulphide on reduction with sulphurous acid. A re-examination of this tetrabromo derivative has shown that it is actually a dihydrotetrabromide of the disulphide (V); three of the four bromine atoms being labile towards hydroiodic acid. The initial action of bromine on 1-thiolbenzthiazole is clearly, therefore, one of oxidation, giving rise to a hydrobromic acid salt of the disulphide which then combines with bromine, yielding the dihydrotetrabromide (V).

The bromination of 1-methylbenzthiazole, which has not previously been examined, presented unusual difficulty. The ultimate product is a hydrotribromide of a monobromo-substitution derivative which is most probably the 5-bromo compound (VI), but its forma-

tion appears to be preceded by that of a true addition product of bromine with the unsubstituted methylbenzthiazole.

This recalls the behaviour of 1-aminobenzthiazole which at low temperatures yields a labile dibromo-addition compound rapidly isomerising to the hydrobromide of 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole (Hunter, *loc. cit.*), and it, therefore, appeared of interest to examine the effect of further bromination on 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole.

At 0°, however, this base underwent nuclear substitution yielding a hydrotribromide of a dibromoaminobenzthiazole whose constitution (VII) follows from the synthesis of the dibromo base, obtained by reduction with sulphurous acid from 2:4-dibromophenylthiocarbimide by way of the thiocarbamide (VIII).

With substitution of hydrogen *ortho* to the nuclear nitrogen atom in 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole by bromine, further halogen substitution is suppressed (*cf.* Dyson, Hunter, Jones, and Styles, *loc. cit.*) and bromination of 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole under the usual conditions gives rise to a tetrabromide (IX), which regenerates the dibromoaminobenzthiazole on treatment with sulphurous acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For the following experiments, sodium-dried bromine (B.D.H.) was used and the chloroform was first dried and thereafter redistilled over phosphorus pentoxide.

1-Chlorobenzthiazole dibromide, prepared by concentrating in a vacuum at laboratory temperature the solution obtained by treating the chlorothiazole (1 g.) in chloroform (5 c.c.) with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent), formed yellow crystals which had m.p. 132° after drying in a vacuum. [Found: Br (total), 48.5; Br (labile),

27.0. Calc. for $C_7H_4NCIS(Br_2)$, Br (total and labile), 48.6 per cent]. It dissolved in sulphurous acid giving a colourless solution which on basification yielded 1-chlorobenzthiazole which was identified by its properties and by its conversion into 1-anilinobenzthiazole (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 1126; 1880, 13, 11), which had m. p. 158° alone and when mixed with an authentic specimen.

1-Phenylbenzthiazole, prepared by the thionation of benzanilide, was redistilled in *vacuo* and recrystallised from dilute alcohol when it formed long needles, m.p. 114° (Bogert and Abrahamson, *loc. cit.*).

1-Phenylbenzthiazole dibromide.—A solution of the base (2 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.6 c.c. in 0.6 c.c. of the same solvent) at 0°, and the mixture was kept in a freezing mixture when the dibromide separated in yellow needles, m.p. 119° after being dried in a vacuum. [Found: Br (total), 44.9; Br (labile), 30.9. $C_{13}H_9NS(Br_2)$ requires Br (total and labile), 43.1 per cent]. On treatment with sulphurous acid, the dibromide regenerated 1-phenylbenzthiazole which was identified by m.p. and mixed m.p. determination.

1-Phenylbenzthiazole tetrabromide.—A specimen of this compound, prepared as already described by one of us, showed the usual discrepancy between determinations for total and labile bromine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 138). The decolorised chloroform layer obtained in iodometric titration was, therefore, separated, the solvent removed on a steam bath and the residue was recrystallised from alcohol. It had m.p. 98° and contained halogen, but it was not found possible to isolate 5-bromo-1-phenylbenzthiazole on account of the closeness of its solubility to that of 1-phenylbenzthiazole in ordinary solvents.

Thermal decomposition.—A freshly prepared specimen of the tetrabromide was heated in an oil-bath at 120° at 5 mm. pressure for 5 minutes, when the compound showed obvious signs of decomposition. The residue gave the following figures on analysis. [Found: Br (total), 42.2; Br (labile), 22.0 per cent], and yielded 1-phenylbenzthiazole unaccompanied by 5-bromo-1-phenylbenzthiazole on reduction with sulphurous acid.

1-Thiolbenzthiazole was prepared as follows:—A mixture of acetanilide (500 g.) and sulphur (300 g.) was heated in a pyrex flask at its b. p. for 53 hours and the sublimated 1:1-bis-benzthiazole (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1880, 13, 1223) was extracted with 60% sulphuric acid (Lauth, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1896, 15, 82), isolated by precipitation with water and purified by sublimation. An intimate mixture of the

bisthiazole (10 g.) and powdered potassium hydroxide (20 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 200° until complete fusion occurred. The mixture was cooled, treated with ice water (100 c.c.) and the alkaline solution of the sodium salt of *o*-aminophenylmercaptan was filtered through asbestos and neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid. The mixture of *o*-aminophenylmercaptan and *o*-aminophenyl-disulphide, so obtained, was extracted with ether and the product was reduced with zinc and concentrated hydrochloric acid in the usual way. A mixture of the zinc salt of *o*-aminophenylmercaptan (2 g.), carbon disulphide (4 c.c.) and alcohol (25 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 6 hours and the oil obtained after removal of the solvent and excess of carbon disulphide was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. On recrystallisation of the precipitated solid from alcohol, 1-thiolbenzthiazole was obtained in yellow needles, m.p. 179°.

Benzthiazolyl-1:1-disulphide dihydrotetrabromide.—A solution of the thiolbenzthiazole (1 g.) in chloroform was treated with bromine (1.5 c.c. in 1.5 c.c. of chloroform) at 0°. The bromo-addition compound formed orange plates which had m.p. 127° (decomp.) after drying. [Found: Br (total), 66.0; Br (labile), 40.6. $C_{14}H_8N_2S_4$, 2 HBr(Br₃) requires Br(total), 65.5; Br(labile), 49.0 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid it yielded benzthiazolyl 1:1-disulphide, m.p. 180°. A mixture of the disulphide and the original thiolbenzthiazole melted at 159°.

Bromination of 1-methylbenzthiazole.—(i) 1G. of 1-methylbenzthiazole (Jacobson, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1069) in chloroform (5 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) at 0°. As no separation of a bromo-addition product took place the solution was concentrated in a vacuum at laboratory temperature, when an orang-eyellow product was obtained, m.p. 76°. [Found: Br(total), 45.5; Br(labile), 27.2 per cent]. (ii) In a similar experiment in which the methylbenzthiazole (1 g. in 20 c.c. of chloroform) was treated with bromine (3 c.c. in 3 c.c. of chloroform), yellow plates were obtained, contaminated by a certain amount of gummy material which was removed by trituration with chloroform. The *hydrotribromide* of the bromomethylbenzthiazole obtained in this way melted at 70°. [Found: Br(total), 64.5; Br(labile), 33.9. C_8H_6NBrS , HBr(Br₂) requires Br(total), 68.2; Br(labile), 34.1 per cent]. The hydrotribromide dissolved in sulphurous acid giving a colourless solution which on basification, extraction with ether and removal of the ether on a steam bath yielded needles of 5(?)*-bromo-1-methylbenzthiazole*, con-

taminated by a small quantity of gummy material which was removed by washing the crystals with ether, m.p. 120°. (Found: Br, 35.8. C_8H_6NBrS requires Br, 35.1 per cent).

Bromination of 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole, the isolation of 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide and the synthesis of 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole from 2:4-dibromophenylthiocarbimide by way of 2:4-dibromophenylthiocarbamide.—(A). Bromine (2 c.c. in 2 c.c. of chloroform) was added to a solution of 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole (1 g.) in chloroform (60 c.c.) at 0°, and the mixture was kept in a freezing mixture when the *hydrotribromide* of 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole separated in beautiful golden plates which were collected on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum. On heating the hydrotribromide lost bromine, becoming colourless, but was still unmelted at 285°. [Found: Br(total), 72.9; Br(labile), 30.3. $C_7H_4N_2Br_2S$, $HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br(total), 72.9; Br(labile), 29.2 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid, basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from alcohol, 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole was obtained, m.p. 261°. (Found: Br, 51.9. $C_7H_4N_2Br_2S$ requires Br, 52.0 per cent).

(B). The 2:4-dibromoaniline used for the following experiments was conveniently prepared as follows:—A suspension of 20 g. finely powdered *p*-bromoacetanilide in cold potassium bicarbonate solution (10 g. in 400 c.c. of water) was mechanically stirred during the addition, drop by drop, of a hypobromous acid solution prepared from precipitated mercuric oxide (80 g.), bromine (20 c.c.) and water (600 c.c.). Stirring was continued for a further hour after completion of the addition of hypobromous acid and the mixture was extracted with chloroform. The *N*-bromo-*p*-bromoacetanilide, obtained by evaporation of the chloroform at laboratory temperature, was heated with a small quantity of glacial acetic acid in an oil-bath at 110–30°, and the cooled melt was recrystallised from alcohol. The dibromoacetanilide obtained in this way was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution was basified with ammonia (d 0.880), when 2:4-dibromoaniline was obtained in small needles, m.p. 79°.

(i) *2:4-Dibromophenylthiocarbimide.*—A solution of 2:4-dibromoaniline (5 g.) in chloroform (15 c.c.) was gradually added to a well-stirred suspension of thiocarbonyl chloride (5 c.c.) in water (80 c.c.). Stirring was continued for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour after the completion of addition of the amine and the mixture was extracted with chloroform.

On recrystallisation of the residue, obtained by removal of the chloroform on a steam bath, from benzene and thereafter from benzene-petroleum, the thiocarbimide was obtained in needles, m.p. 63°. (Found: Br, 54·5. $C_7H_3NBr_2S$ requires Br, 54·4 per cent).

(ii) *2:4-Dibromophenylthiocarbamide*, prepared by heating a mixture of the dibromophenylthiocarbimide (2 g.), absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and ammonia (d 0·880, 3 c.c.) for 20 minutes under reflux, separated from alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 171°. (Found: Br, 51·5. $C_7H_6N_2Br_2S$ requires Br, 51·6 per cent).

(iii) 1 G. of 2:4-dibromophenylthiocarbamide in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a steam bath under reflux for 15 minutes. As there was no separation of a hydroperbromide on cooling, the solution was concentrated in a vacuum and the product was reduced with sulphurous acid in the usual way. On crystallisation from alcohol, 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole was obtained as small needles, m.p. 259° which remained unaltered when mixed with the specimen obtained by bromination of 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole.

3:5-Dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole tetrabromide.—A saturated solution of 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole in 50 c. c. of chloroform was cooled and treated with bromine (3 c. c. in 3 c. c. of chloroform). As no separation of a bromo-addition compound occurred, the solution was concentrated in a vacuum at laboratory temperature, when the tetrabromide crystallised in glistening orange needles, which lost bromine on heating but were still unmelted at 285°. [Found: Br, (total), 76·95. $C_7H_4N_2Br_2S$ (Br_4) requires Br (total), 76·4 per cent]. A satisfactory determination of labile bromine could not be made owing to the very low solubility of the compound in chloroform. On reduction with sulphurous acid, the tetrabromide regenerated the original 3:5-dibromo-1-aminobenzthiazole.

Note on the action of bromine on thiobenzanilide.—In view of the formal similarity between Jacobson's synthesis of 1-substituted benzthiazoles from thioanilides and the preparation of 1-aminobenzthiazoles from arylthiocarbamides and bromine, it occurred to us that it might be possible to obtain 1-phenylbenzthiazole by treatment of thiobenzanilide in chloroform with bromine under the usual conditions of thiazole cyclisation of arylthiocarbamides. The following experiment was therefore made.—A solution of thiobenzanilide (0·5 g.) in chloroform (10 c. c.) was treated with bromine (0·5 c. c. in 0·5 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 10 minutes when hydrogen bromide was evolved, cooled

and concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The product obtained by reduction with sulphurous acid, basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from alcohol, however, differed strikingly from both 1-phenylbenzthiazole and 5-bromo-1-phenylbenzthiazole and melted at 206°. No trace of 1-phenylbenzthiazole, which is readily recognised when present in small quantities by its characteristic odour of tea roses, could be detected. It, therefore, appears that the duplicated thioamide triad system present in thio-carbamides, is necessary to thiazole cyclisation by bromine.

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Received August 14, 1933.